

INFLUENCE OF TEXTILE DESIGN PARAMETERS ON DRAPEABILITY OF WARP-KNIT NCF

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ABSTRACT

Characterising the drapeability of reinforcement fabrics, is one of the most sought after abilities of those designing composite processes and components. This is not surprising as composite processes are being considered in a greater range of fields and applications. Drapeability effects are formed by the irregular displacement of fibres. This displacement can occur within the textile plane and result in fibre disorientations, undulations and gaps or the fibres can be pushed into the third dimension - forming wrinkles.

To measure such effects in NCF, the Textechno Drapetest automatic drapeability tester was used on a set of textiles that were chosen to show the influence of textile design parameters on drapeability effects. The Textechno Drapetest uses a sophisticated digital image analysis system to measure the position and direction of fibres and conclude from this information on the extent and intensity of drapeability effects in the textile surface. To measure effects outside the surface, i.e. wrinkles, a laser triangulation scanner is employed. The textiles were varied in the production parameters of stitch point distance in machine direction (MD) and cross direction (CD), the weight per area, and the stitch pattern (tricot and chain). A full factorial experimental design was chosen for a thorough investigation of these parameters.

The measurements showed a significant influence of the stitch yarn on the formation of effects. Especially the density of stitch points is a parameter that lets the textile producer control the behaviour of the textile when they are formed into a doubly curved three dimensional shape. To control the gap formation, however, the spacing of the stitch points in machine or in crosswise direction is also of importance with a shorter stitch length decreasing the forming of gaps more than a tighter stitch yarn pitch.

1 INTRODUCTION

The classical definition of drapeability in the field of composite manufacturing is the capability of a fabric to adhere to a complex shape. This has resulted in the classification of well drapeable and badly drapeable fabrics. Good drapeability by this definition means that a textile can adhere to a challenging shape without the formation of wrinkles [1]. While wrinkles can be described as the definite drapeability defect for woven fabrics, for the class of non-crimp-fabrics (NCF), other effects have to be considered as well. In contrast to woven structures the tows in NCF can slide within the fabric plane, as they are not interlocked with the tows of a different orientation [2]. This leads to the causation of additional drapeability effects such as gaps and fibre undulations [3]. Such sliding is unavoidable and necessary to make the fabric drapeable at all. The resulting effects can thus not be considered as defects in general [4]. However, overly strong formation of such effects can negatively influence laminate properties, so that it is necessary to understand and describe the formation of such effects. So a well drapeable fabric under the classic definition forms no wrinkles but may display gaps and undulations that could be detrimental to the mechanical performance of the final component. It

becomes increasingly clear, that the definition of drapeability must be expanded to include in-plane drapeability effects as well and to find a measure that goes beyond a qualitative description.

For woven reinforcement fabrics, much research has been carried out. Both testing and modelling capabilities of such textiles are well developed and the mechanics are understood [5]. The dominant textile mechanic is the shear of the fabric, so that the warp and weft yarns will be moved out of their 90° orientation to each other during the draping process. If a fabric is sheared to much, it will start to wrinkle. The onset of this wrinkling depends on the fabric's weave type, with weaves that produce more interlock points having less drapeability and a lower critical shear angle [6].

To measure the shear behaviour of woven fabrics, mainly the trellis frame (picture frame) and bias extension test are in use [7] although a two axis extension test exists as well, but requires more complicated testing equipment [8]. The test setups have also been coupled with image analysis setups, to measure the strain field of the sample and to measure the shear angle of the fabric which is not always equal to the shear angle of the frame [9]. The trellis frame and bias extension have also been applied to NCF material, but success here has been lower than with woven fabrics [10]. One reason is that even biaxial NCF incorporate three yarn systems, because of the additional stitch yarn. This means that orientation of the fabric sample in the frame is a factor, since the NCF is not orthotropic. Furthermore, measuring the shear behaviour is not sufficient to describe the drapeability of NCF due to the sliding mechanic described above.

2 MEASUREMENT METHOD

The measurements in this paper were conducted with the Textechno Drapetest automatic drapeability tester [11]. It is based on the hemispherical drapeability test that uses the principle of pushing a hemispherical reference body against a clamped textile sample to forcibly drape the textile into that shape [12]. Within the scope of a joint research project, this method was enhanced by a sophisticated digital image analysis system, as proposed earlier [13], to create the Drapetest. Contrary to the digital image correlation systems mentioned above, the system employed in the Drapetest is not for measuring displacements to map a strain field, but to measure singular drapeability effects. To achieve this, the tester is equipped with three optical systems. A fixed overhead camera can take images of the entire sample to record large scale deformations. A high resolution detail camera tracks the textile surface, while it is being deformed. With its resolution of 64 pixel/mm, it can detect small scale fibre movements. Lastly, a laser line-scanner creates a topographical image of the deformed sample. The computer measures the direction of all visible fibres with the method of edge detection [14]. From this, the fibre orientation can be measured both globally and locally. Based on the information of fibre orientation also gaps can be discovered. Additionally, the force necessary for the deformation is recorded.

The deformation is applied in discrete, user definable steps. At each step the surface of the sample is scanned with the described optical systems. The sample is rotated to expose all sides to the detail camera and the laser. This procedure is repeated for every defined step. This automatic operation makes it feasible to test larger sample batches.

Figure 1: Measurement principle of the Drapetest (Source: Textechno)

From these data sources, quantitative information on the effects that have formed can be derived. A set of characteristic values (Table 1) was chosen that describe the effects that can be observed, both in magnitude and intensity.

Name	Symbol	Unit
Force	F	N
Gap width	G_W	mm
Gap percentage	G_P	%
Gap shape	G_S	-
Fibre angle shift	$\Delta\alpha$	degree
Undulations	$\Delta\alpha_{loc}$	degree
Loops	Ω	mm ²
Waviness (out-of-plane)	λ	mm
Non-circularity	θ	%

Table 1: Characteristic values to describe drapeability effects in NCF

All measurements are a function of the displacement of the reference body and the position on the reference body. Dependent on the fibre orientations chosen in the design of the NCF each position corresponds with a certain fibre angle and thus a different mechanical response of the fabric. The position is defined in the coordinate system of the undeformed fabric with values between 90° and -90°, with 0° always being the machine direction (MD) parallel to the stitch yarn. Because the reference body possesses rotational symmetry, the results are symmetrical as well, with values being equal at positions that are at opposite sides of the body, i.e. with 180° fibre angle difference.

One motivation for the development of the Drapetest device were the difficulties in comparing data between individual designs of common drapeability test setups such as the trellis frame or the bias extension test, as shown by the international benchmarking effort [7]. The Drapetest is available as an industrially built device so that each copy should produce the same results. The testing methodology and requirements for the testing device have been publicized as DIN SPEC 8100 [15]. This will allow other test devices to be built to the same standards to improve inter-laboratorial comparability.

3 MATERIAL (DESIGN SPACE)

The formation of drapeability effects is influenced, as mentioned above, by the in-plane movement of tows which in turn is inhibited by the warp-knit stitching yarns. For the stitching all parameters of classical warp-knitting can be adjusted when designing the NCF. It is therefore necessary to investigate the influence of the stitching parameters on the drapeability effect formation, so that the ideal fabric can be selected. To achieve this, a number of textile design parameters were chosen which were expected to have the greatest influence on the formation of the drapeability effects of interest.

The chosen parameters (Table 2) were varied in a full factorial design space. The stitch point distance in the cross direction is usually given as the gauge pitch in needles per inch. To ease the comparison with the stitch length, these values have been converted to the distance of the warp pillars in mm. The distances of the stitch points were varied in such a way as to show the influence of choosing their spacing in either direction.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Range
Stitch point distance 1 (machine direction MD)	l	mm	2.5, 5, 10
Stitch point distance 2 (cross direction CD)	c	mm	2.5, 5, 10
Mass per area	W	g/m ²	200, 300, 400, 600
Pattern type	-	-	Pillar, tricot

Table 2: Parameters varied for the study about textile design influences on drapeability effects

The result of these variations can be better understood by looking at the fabric appearance depending on the stitch pattern (Figure 2). By increasing both the MD and CD values equally, the number of stitches per area unit decreases with the “free area” between the stitch points remaining a square. The number of stitch points can also be decreased by increasing the distance in only one direction. This will result in anisotropy in the stitching pattern, visualised by the free area becoming rectangular. Anisotropy can be controlled by either increasing the MD or CD distance, effectively creating a horizontally or vertically oriented free area. This means that moving along the verticals of the table shown in Figure 2 allows comparing fabrics with free areas of the same size but different anisotropy (right to left) or such with equal anisotropy but different free areas (i.e. number of stitch points per unit area).

Figure 2: Development of different fabric variations by changing the stitch point distance in machine direction (MD) and crosswise direction (CD); (a) maximum number of stitch points, isotropic distribution; (b) anisotropic distribution of stitch points; (c) isotropic distribution with lower number of stitch points; (d) anisotropic distribution with different bias

All NCF in this study are biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ glass fibre fabrics. The stitch yarn tension was kept as constant as possible in the manufacturing process at $4\text{cN} \pm 0.4\text{cN}$. The fabrics were produced on a Karl Mayer Malitronic Multiaxial. This paper will focus on the results of one set of nine fabrics with varying stitch lengths but constant weight per area and pattern type.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Force

The draping force, i.e. the force necessary to form the fabric is a good overall measure for the ease to make a fabric adhere to a certain shape. It is a global value that gives no direct indication of the formation of drapeability effects or the quality of the result. Nevertheless it should be considered to gain a first overview of the fabrics response to a forced deformation. The force as a function of displacement for a NCF with a stitching length $l = 5$ mm and a crosswise stitch point distance of $c = 5$ mm is shown in Figure 3. This combination can be considered the base fabric for the subset shown in this paper,. The test is aborted after 90 mm of displacement because the fabric starts to move out of the blank holder which leads to a drop in the draping force. The curve between 20 mm and 80 mm displacement is close to linear, so that the force at 80 mm displacement can be considered as a characterizing value for the fabric.

Figure 3: Force over Displacement diagram for a NCF with $c = 5$ mm, $l = 5$ mm, $W = 400$ g/m²

Comparing the drapeability forces for all nine NCF (Figure 4), the forces align with the looseness of the stitching patterns. Along the downward diagonals from left to right the fabrics grow looser and consequently the draping force is reduced. Along the upward verticals from left to right, the free area is equal and the draping forces are close to constant as well, with the exception of the lowest diagonal.

	$c = 2.5$ mm	$c = 5$ mm	$c = 10$ mm
$l = 2.5$ mm	1804.8	1427.2	1100.8
$l = 5$ mm	1369.8	1071.3	764.0
$l = 10$ mm	1080.9	1009.0	682.3

Figure 4: Draping forces in cN at 80 mm displacement for all nine fabrics

4.2 Gaps

Gaps are localized drapeability effects that form as openings in the textile surface when yarns slide. The hypothesis is that they are highly dependent on the size of the free area. The second hypothesis is that the gaps are influenced by the bias of the free area. The alignment of the free area along the

machine direction might influence the sliding mechanism and therefore the gap formation differently than a free area aligned in the crosswise direction.

The results for the gaps are dependent on the fibre angle relative to the reference body (Figure 5). The results for those positions 180° in opposition to each other are mirrored so it is not necessary to use both in the analysis, thus reducing the amount of data that must be regarded. The standard deviation of the measurements is between 3% and 10% across the six samples. The standard deviation of measured gaps in the undeformed samples is also in this range, this leads to the conclusion, that it is the variation already present in the fabric samples.

Figure 5: Gap formation for a NCF with $c = 5 \text{ mm}$, $l = 5 \text{ mm}$, $G = 400 \text{ g/m}^2$; the error bars show the standard deviation of six tested samples

The gap formation is dependent on the stitching of the NCF, as expected, and as can be seen in Figure 6. The fabrics are sorted from more closely knit to looser from top left to bottom right. The looser fabrics show a much larger growth in gaps than the more tightly bound fabrics. This is unsurprising, as more sliding is possible for the rovings. Most gaps form in the fabric position of 45° , which is orthogonal to the top fabric layer. This is also expected as in this position the rovings slide laterally along the surface of the reference body and the fabric surface is split open by this movement. The most tightly knit fabric shows a surprising amount of gaps, even though the close spacing of the stitch yarns should inhibit any sliding. The gaps in this fabric are due to the stitching itself and not the draping since almost the same amount of gaps is already present in the undeformed samples. The stitching is so closely spaced in both directions, that the small gaps induced by the yarn penetrating the textile surface melt together to form a large number of continuous channels across the fabric.

The results also show that the bias of the free area must not be neglected. Increasing the stitch yarn pitch c in the crosswise direction has less influence on the growth of gaps than increasing the stitching length l . The mechanism behind this is that when the stitch yarn is loaded in a direction 45° to the machine direction, the knitwear embedded in the NCF with the smaller stitch length is stiffer because the distance to the next fixed-point is shorter.

Gap formation in the 0° direction (first area of predominant shear) is small because tensioning of the stitch yarn minimizes roving movement in the fabric. In contrast the second area of shear (90° direction) shows more gaps, here the stitch yarn is in compression and does not restrict roving movement.

Figure 6: Amount of gaps in percent of fabric surface as function of stitch distances, displacement and fibre angle

4.3 Fibre Angle

The fibre angle in the fabric must change when the fabric is forced into the three dimensional shape. This cannot be avoided and thus cannot be classified as a defect as such. Nevertheless, changes in fibre angle naturally influence the mechanical properties. It is therefore helpful for the designer to know the change of fibre angle that must be reflected in the calculations and choice of material.

The fibre angle of an area is determined by the mean direction of all resolved fibres in that area. The change of fibre angle is measured by comparing the fibre angle of the deformed state with the one measured in the flat state of the same area. The measured change of fibre angle is a function of the position and displacement.

The influence of the stitch yarn pattern on the fibre angle change is shown in Figure 8. The diagrams are arranged same as before, with the tightest knit in the upper left and the loosest in the bottom right. The influence of the tightness or looseness is reversed to the one observed for the gap formation. The more tightly knit NCF show greater fibre angle shift than the looser ones. No influence of the free area bias can be observed, with fabrics along the diagonals from bottom left to top right behaving equally. The governing influence seems to be alone the number of stitch points per area. Remarkable is the difference between the two shear areas at 0° and 90° (see Figure 7). The area of so called “positive shear” [2] at 0° fabric angle with the stitch yarn in tension shows negligible amounts of fibre angle change. The biggest shift in fibre angle occurs at the second shear area of “negative shear” where the stitch yarn is in compression. This behaviour is similar to what has been in recorded in the more usual trellis frame experiments. Interestingly, the behaviour at 45° is contrary to the general trend of lower fibre angle shift in the looser fabrics. This can be explained by the described easy sliding of the rovings at this position. This leads also to in-plane fibre bending and undulations which also result in deviation from the initial fibre angle.

Figure 7: Fibre angle shift for a region of positive shear (0°) and negative shear (90°) for the same sample of the same NCF ($c = 2.5$ mm, $l = 2.5$ mm). The thin blue line shows the measured fibre angle in the deformed state, the dotted purple line the 45° fibre angle of the flat sample.

Figure 8: The change in fibre angle as a function of stitch distance in both directions, initial fibre orientation and displacement

5 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion the following insights into the formation of drapeability effects were gained. The Textechno Drapetest is capable of measuring effects such as gaps and fibre angles that occur in NCF. Its semi-automated nature and industrial manufacturing make it ideal for large measurement campaigns with repeatable results. The ability to quantify such effects as functions of deformation and fibre angle is a big step beyond the state of the art.

The formation of drapeability effects in NCF is largely dependent on the stitch yarn pattern. A full factorial design space was chosen to thoroughly investigate the influence of the stitch point density and distribution in machine and crosswise direction on the effects. As material $\pm 45^\circ$ glass fibre NCF were used.

The measurements with the drapeability tester were able to reproduce effects observed before during trellis frame tests thus validating the measurement principle of this new test setup. The non orthotropic behaviour of NCF that is found in the literature could be observed very clearly in the new tests. Results for the regions of shear with the stitch yarn in tension and the stitch yarn in compression showed large differences. Those regions with the stitch yarn in tension showed very low effect formation either for gaps or fibre angle shifts.

From the experimental results it could be concluded that stitch point density is an important but not the only factor influencing gaps and fibre angles. Draping forces increase with increasing stitch point density, similar to the behaviour of woven fabrics with higher density of cross-over points. However, when measuring the gaps in NCF the stitch point density was found to be not sufficient to explain the results. Instead the distribution of the stitch points in machine and crosswise direction must also be considered. NCF with the same amount of stitching points but a shorter stitching length were found to produce less gaps than those with longer stitching length and closer stitching yarn pitch.

This behaviour could not be found when measuring the change of fibre angle due to the deformation. For the fibre angle shift, the stitch point density remains the governing parameter.

6 OUTLOOK

This paper could only show a small amount of the data collected during the measurements. Future work will include further analysis of the gap formation especially with regard to shape and size of individual gaps. The fibre angle can also be broken down further to show local variations of the fibre angle, i.e. undulations. Three-dimensional effects, such as wrinkles or loops will be investigated to establish a link between in-plane and out-of-plane drapeability effects.

The influence of the stitch yarn pattern will be amended by investigating NCF with tricot stitching. Tricot knit NCF usually exhibit draping behaviour quite different to the pillar knit NCF shown in this paper.

Beyond the analysis of the phenomena observed in the experiments, a more theoretical application for the measurements must be found. The quantitative nature of the data makes it ideal to use in either numerical or analytical calculations.

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